

Semi-solid-state Li-ion batteries functionally integrated in composite structures for next generation hybrid electric airliner

CLEAN SKY 2

H2020 JTII-CS2-2020-CfP11-THT-11

High Power density / multifunctional electrical storage solutions for aeronautic applications

GA # 101007577

Deliverable No.	SOLIFLY D4.1	
Deliverable Title	Airworthiness assessment for structural batteries	
Deliverable Date	2023-09-30	
Deliverable Type	REPORT	
Dissemination level	Public	
Author(s)	Michele Guida and Gennaro di Mauro (UNINA Federico II)	2023-08-28
Reviewer	Fulvio Romano and Umberto Mercurio (CIRA); Felix Steinke (CCI)	2023-09-14
Approver	Helmut Kuehnelt (AIT)	2023-12-11
Status	Final	2023-12-21

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking programme under Grant Agreement no. 101007577. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contents

1	Introduction.....	3
2	Certification requirements for structural batteries.....	4
3	Certification requirements of composite aircraft structures	6
3.1	Static strength substantiation	6
3.2	Fatigue and damage tolerance	9
3.2.1	Damage tolerance evaluation.....	9
3.2.2	Fatigue evaluation	11
4	Certification requirements of electrical equipment and installations	13
4.1	System safety assessment.....	13
4.2	Health monitoring.....	14
4.3	Flammability.....	14
4.4	Continued airworthiness.....	14
4.5	Aircraft battery maintenance.....	15
4.6	Aircraft battery replacement	16
4.7	Aircraft battery storage and handling.....	16
5	Conclusions.....	18
6	References	19

Content of figures

Figure 1: Building block approach scheme, [5].	8
Figure 2: Reduced Sampling technique, [5].....	8
Figure 3: Schematic diagram of design load levels versus categories of damage severity, [5].....	11

Nomenclature

Acronym / Short Name	
UD	UniDirectional
OPFM	Onera progressive failure Model
CCF	multifunctional Coated Carbon Fibres material
RMS	Reinforced Multilayer Stack
SB	Structural Batteries
ILSS	InterLaminar Shear Strength
FE	Finite Element

1 Introduction

Electrification of aircraft systems is key for increasing efficiency and reducing climate impact of air transport towards the European net-zero goal. The functional integration of structural capabilities and electrical energy storage in the form of structural batteries (SB) is considered as a low TRL technology with the potential to reduce the impact of battery energy storage on the overall aircraft weight. So far, structural batteries have been mainly studied at material level, largely neglecting their integration into aircraft structures.

The CleanSky2 THT project SOLIFLY is developing further structural batteries for aeronautical applications with two cell concepts, one with coated carbon fibres acting as structural and electrically conductive components, and another with laminate structural electrodes. The project puts particular emphasis on their integration into CFRP laminates that are compatible with aeronautical manufacturing processes.

This report fixes some general considerations about certification requirements on composite material structures and the current trend of certification agencies to move towards a performance-based regulations. This document may represent a reference for structural composite batteries, for which there are still no well-defined certification requirements. Assuming this approach is valid, an airworthy solution for certification of composite structures with embedded structural batteries is given, providing an innovative interpretation of existing regulations, in compliance with current trends.

2 Certification requirements for structural batteries

The possibility to embed structural batteries into aeronautical structures is surely an open question from a certification point of view. The effort of certification agencies in this field is very important to set an answer. The European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) with the re-written CS-23, [9] and [10] paves the way for a new era in General Aviation industry. This CS-23 specifications are dedicated to:

- Aeroplanes in the normal, utility, and aerobatic categories that have a seating configuration, excluding the pilot seat(s), of nine or fewer and a maximum certified take-off weight of 5670 kg (12 500 lb) or less;
- Propeller-driven, twin-engine aeroplanes in the commuter category that have a seating configuration, excluding the pilots seat(s), of 19 or fewer and a maximum certified take-off weight of 8618 kg (19 000 lb) or less.

CS-23 was changed to make the criteria more "high level," keeping the essential intents for safety but deleting those that were connected to specific technology, forms, or functions (or were prescriptive).

The goal was to simplify and speed the bureaucratic procedure that was frequently required for the introduction of technical improvements, by defining new ad hoc Special Conditions that would be included in the certification base.

With the new CS 23, these "novelties" may now be controlled directly at the "Means of Compliance" level (one level below the requirements), indicating the activities to be done to verify compliance with the more general security need.

This strategy is moving towards performance-based regulations [1], a regulatory approach that focuses on desired, measurable outcomes. In this way the trend is given of introducing new integrated technologies and applications to the aviation industry, making them airworthy. The priority remains the safety, and the structures must not reduce the existing level of safety, but this approach guarantees flexibility and potential safety benefits for industry.

This approach is especially aimed at new generation structures, that fall under the category of advanced manufacturing, meaning the ones where the material is made concurrently with the part. It involves creating final, or near-final, material properties at the same time the part is manufactured. Examples of advanced manufacturing are surely composite components and thus, structural batteries themselves. A more formal definition could be one where material consolidates using a series of process steps requiring strict controls to achieve near-final part geometry and the desired repeatable performance characteristics, and where variation in any process step may have measurable effects on the material characteristics that in turn affect product performance.

Under this approach, the first step for certification of any advanced material and process, in any application, is the material and process control. It is the most critical phase since the materials and processes must be defined and stable. Material and process definition is the design envelope space in which compliance must be demonstrated.

Regulations require to define the configuration and design features of the product with sufficient detail to ensure the final product will comply with the applicable airworthiness requirements.

Three items are needed to check that the Material and Process Control is correctly carried out:

- The feedstock material must be certified. For composites, this is more than just laminate materials, meaning that also core, adhesive, and non-fly away materials need to be certified. Specifically for structural batteries certified materials must be available, meaning not only the carbon fiber, but also the matrix and the materials adopted to make the structural battery materials capable of storing electrical energy. In this instance, the part needs to be evaluated for the final SB electrode coatings/electrolyte as well as for passive components (current collector foils) and active components, additives, binders, etc. In addition, to notice is that the aim is to realize a composite

structure within which several structural batteries are embedded and connected by wires. This means that also the wires themselves must be certified.

- The process adopted to convert the feedstock material to a part has to be stable and repeatable. To notice is that using new materials and processes means that existing methods and design guides may not be appropriate or applicable.
- The final part material must ensure that the required chemical, physical and mechanical properties are achieved. With a particular reference to Structural Batteries, size effects meaning the interaction between microstructures with structural geometry must be accounted.

In that context standardization organizations and shared databases become increasingly important. The most widely used standard for verifying the airworthiness of a composite material is the FAR part 25 from Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) [2].

In addition, the AGATE [3] and NCAMP [4] programs are two databases that provide a list of composite materials certified according to FAR part 25 regulations, reporting, in addition, the entire material certification procedure.

Once the material and process control are completed, compliance with airworthiness requirements must be demonstrated.

3 Certification requirements of composite aircraft structures

What is described in this chapter should be regarded as applicable to all composite structures regardless of aircraft category, since the concept of a structural battery is to be considered as a multifunctional composite material to be made airworthy and is fully included in the certification of an aeronautical product, [9] and [10].

The rapid development of composite materials over the past three decades and their use in fields such as the aeronautical one, in which the safety requirements are particularly stringent, has given rise to the need for an accurate characterization of these materials. Mechanical tests on materials and structural details are conducted to achieve one or more of the following objectives:

- characterization of materials or production processes;
- development of project allowables;
- qualification of materials for specific applications;
- quality control;
- evaluation of strength and durability by applying prolonged or cyclical loads;
- estimation of the influence of damage and degradation due, e.g., to environmental conditions.

Metal alloys produced for aerospace applications are available in standard compositions and their properties are now well characterized. Composite materials, on the other hand, are produced at the same time as the structural component and for this reason they can have a wide range of properties, which depend on the fiber, the resin and process used. It has been found that some characteristics of the composites are also strongly influenced by environmental conditions. Consequently, the requirements for the certification of composite structures are much more stringent than those required for metals. That is due to the aim of reaching the same level of safety in aeronautical field, despite the material adopted to realize the structure. In 1978 the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) issued the Advisory Circular (AC) 20-107, [5], on the certification of aeronautical structures in composite materials, the European equivalent is AMC 20-29 issued as Annex II in 2010, [6]. This is a document which specifies the need to determine the mechanical properties of the material examined by conducting targeted experimental tests:

- Static test, in which the structure is subjected to 150% of the Design Limit Load (DLL), i.e., to the Ultimate Load; these tests are used, especially at high temperatures, to evaluate the resistance and long-term dimensional stability by subjecting the material samples to lower percentages of the static breaking stress σ_u (typically 10 ÷ 50% of σ_u).
- Fatigue tests on primary structures; the cyclical load stresses allow to measure the resistance to degradation and breakage due to loads varying over time. The frequency of application is generally low to avoid excessive heating of the specimens: in the case of composites, it is between 5 Hz and 10 Hz. The cyclic loads can be of constant amplitude or follow load spectra representative of the real operating conditions of a particular structure.
- Damage tolerance compliance and impact resistance of primary structures. These tests are used to quantify the resistance capacity of the material to impact and penetration. The specimens are impacted by means of indenters and impactors of various sizes.

3.1 Static strength substantiation

The properties of composite materials determine numerous difficulties that must be constantly kept in mind. The structural static strength substantiation of a composite design should consider all critical load cases and associated failure modes. It should also include effects of environment (including structural residual stresses induced during the fabrication process), material and process variability, non-detectable defects or any defects that are allowed by the quality control. The static strength of the composite design should be performed through a program of component ultimate load tests in the appropriate environment to demonstrate the adequacy of the analysis supported by subcomponent, element and coupon tests, or

component tests to accepted lower load levels. The necessary experience to validate an analysis should include previous component ultimate load tests with similar designs, material systems, and load cases.

The effects of repeated loading and environmental exposure which may result in material property degradation should be addressed in the static strength evaluation. This can be shown by analysis supported by test evidence, by tests at the coupon, element or subcomponent level, as appropriate, or alternatively by relevant existing data. For critical loading conditions, three approaches exist to account for prior repeated loading and/or environmental exposure in the full-scale static test:

- In the first approach, the full-scale static test should be conducted on structure with prior repeated loading and conditioned to simulate the critical environmental exposure and then tested in that environment.
- The second approach relies upon coupon, element, and subcomponent test data to determine the effect of repeated loading and environmental exposure on static strength. The degradation characterized by these tests should then be accounted for in the full-scale static strength demonstration test (e.g., overload factors), or in analysis of these results (e.g., showing a positive margin of safety with design values that include the degrading effects of environment and repeated load).
- In practice, aspects of the first two approaches may be combined to get the desired result (e.g., a full-scale static test may be performed at critical operating temperature with a load factor to account for moisture absorbed over the aircraft structure's life). Alternate means to account for environment using validated tests and analyses (e.g., an equivalent temperature enhancement to account for the effect of moisture without chemically altering the material) may be proposed by the applicant to the administrator for approval.

The strength of the composite structure should be reliably established, incrementally, through a program of analysis and a series of tests conducted using specimens of varying levels of complexity. The reference is to the so-called building block approach, in which tests and analyses at the coupon, element, details, and subcomponent levels can be used to address the issues of variability, environment, structural discontinuity (e.g., joints, cut-outs or other stress risers), damage, manufacturing defects, and design or process-specific details. This approach allows to collect data for sufficient analysis correlation and to enhance the comprehension of variations occurring when scaling up the structure, following an economically friendly approach. The lessons learned from initial tests also help avoiding early failures in more complex full-scale tests, which are more costly to conduct and often occur later in a certification program schedule.

Figure 1 provides an example of building block approach for a fixed wing static strength substantiation. The large quantity of tests needed to provide a statistical basis comes from the lowest levels (coupons and elements) and the performance of structural details are validated in a lesser number of subcomponent and component tests. Detail and subcomponent tests may be used to validate the ability of analysis methods to predict local strains and failure modes.

Successful static strength substantiation of composite structures has traditionally depended on proper consideration of stress concentrations (e.g., notch sensitivity of details and impact damage), competing failure modes, and out-of-plane loads. A complete building block approach to composite structural substantiation addresses most critical structural issues in test articles with increasing levels of complexity such that many areas of reliable performance can be demonstrated prior to the component tests. The details and subcomponent testing should establish failure criteria and account for impact damage in assembled composite structures. Component tests are needed to provide the final validation accounting for combined loads and complex load paths, which include some out-of-plane effects. When using the building block approach, the critical load cases and associated failure modes would be identified for component tests using the analytical methods, which are supported by test validation.

Figure 1: Building block approach scheme, [5].

The static test articles should be fabricated and assembled in accordance with production specifications and processes so that the test articles are representative of production structure including defects consistent with the limits established by manufacturing acceptance criteria. The material and processing variability of the composite structure should be considered in the static strength substantiation. This is primarily achieved by establishing sufficient process and quality controls to manufacture structure and reliably substantiate the required strength by test and analysis. The scatter in strength properties due to variability in materials and processes are characterized by proper allowable or design values. To take it into account, a minimum of 36 specimens from at least 6 different batches for each property and environmental condition of interest should be considered, meaning the application of the so-called Reduced sampling technique. In Figure 2 an example of this technique is schematically provided.

Figure 2: Reduced Sampling technique, [5].

When the detail, subcomponent and component tests show that local strains are adequately predicted, and positive margins of safety exist using a validated analysis everywhere on the structure, then proof of static strength is said to be substantiated using analysis supported by test evidence. Alternatively, in the absence of sufficient building block test data and analysis validation, overloads are needed in the component test to gain proof of static strength for the structure using an approach referred to as substantiated by tests. The overload factors applied in this case need to be substantiated either through tests or experience and must account for the expected material and process variation. Most of the tests are conducted under static loads of traction, compression or shear. It is also possible to apply flexural loads, which stress the specimens to combined tension, compression and shear. The application of static loads can be either of short duration (few minutes), or prolonged for weeks and months. These tests are used especially at high temperatures, to evaluate long-term strength and dimensional stability by subjecting the material samples to lower percentages of the static stress σ_u (typically 10÷50% of σ_u).

3.2 Fatigue and damage tolerance

The evaluation of composite structures must show that catastrophic failure due to fatigue, environmental effects, manufacturing defects, or accidental damage will be avoided throughout the operational life of the aircraft. The nature and extent of analysis on complete structures or portions of it will depend upon applicable previous designs, construction, tests, and service experience on similar structures.

When establishing details for the damage tolerance and fatigue evaluation, attention should be given to a thorough damage threat assessment, geometry, inspectability, good design practice, and the damaging types of the considered structure. To notice are the following observations:

- Composite damage tolerance and fatigue performance is strongly dependent on structural design details (e.g., skin laminate stacking sequence, damage arrestment features, and structural redundancy).
- Composite damage tolerance and fatigue evaluations require substantiation in component tests unless experience with similar designs, material systems, and loadings is available to demonstrate the adequacy of the analysis supported by coupons, elements, and subcomponent tests.
- Final static strength, fatigue, and damage tolerance substantiation may be gained in testing a single component test article if sufficient building block test evidence exists to ensure that the selected sequence of repeated and static loading yield results representative of service or provide a conservative evaluation.
- Peak repeated loads are needed to practically demonstrate the fatigue and damage tolerance of composite aircraft structure in a limited number of component tests.

3.2.1 Damage tolerance evaluation

Damage tolerance evaluation starts with identification of structure whose failure would reduce the structural integrity of the aircraft. A damage threat assessment must be performed for the structure to determine possible locations, types, and sizes of damage considering fatigue, environmental effects, intrinsic flaws, and foreign object impact or other accidental damage that may occur during manufacture, operation or maintenance. There are currently very few industry standards that outline the critical damage threats for particular composite structural applications with enough detail to establish the necessary design criteria or test and analysis protocol for complete damage tolerance evaluation.

Some factors to consider in development of a damage threat assessment for a particular composite structure include part function, location on the airplane, past service data, accidental damage threats, environmental exposure, impact damage resistance, durability of structural details, and anomalous service or maintenance handling events that can overload or damage the part. Foreign object impact is another aspect to keep in mind in the damage threat assessment. This is needed to identify impact damage severity and detectability for design and maintenance. It should include any available damage data collected from service plus an

impact survey, meaning of impact tests performed on representative structure subjected to boundary conditions characteristic of the real structure. Many different impact scenarios and locations should be considered in the survey, which has a goal of identifying the most critical impacts possible. When simulating accidental impact damage at representative energy levels, blunt or sharp impactors of different sizes and shapes should be selected to cause the most critical and least detectable damage, according to the load conditions. Specifically, impact surveys should consider a wide range of conceivable impacts, including runway or ground debris, tool drops, and vehicle collisions. This consideration is important in defining design criteria, inspection methods, and repeat inspection intervals for maintenance. Once a damage threat assessment is completed, various damage types can be classified into five categories of increasing damage severity, see Figure 3:

- the first category includes allowable damages that may go undetected by field inspection and allowable manufacturing defects. Structural substantiation includes demonstration of a reliable service life, while retaining ultimate load capability. Some examples of damages belonging to this category are the barely visible impact damages (BVID) and allowable defects caused in manufacturing or service (e.g., small delamination, porosity, small scratches, gouges, and minor environmental damage) that have substantiation data showing ultimate load is retained for the life of an aircraft structure;
- the second category includes damages that can be reliably detected by field inspections performed at specified intervals. Structural substantiation includes demonstration of a reliable inspection method and interval while retaining loads above limit load capability. The residual strength for a damage of this category may depend on the chosen inspection interval and the method of inspection. Some examples of damages included in this category are visible impact damage (VID), deep gouges or scratches, manufacturing mistakes not evident in the factory, detectable delamination or debonding, and major local heat or environmental degradation that will sustain sufficient residual strength until found. This type of damage should not grow or, if slow or arrested growth occurs, the level of residual strength retained for the inspection interval is sufficiently above limit load capability;
- the third category includes damages that can be reliably detected within a few flights of occurrence by maintenance personnel. Such damage must be in a location such that it is obvious by clearly visible evidence or cause other indications of potential damage that becomes obvious in a short time interval because of loss of the part form, fit or function. Both indications of significant damage warrant an expanded inspection to identify the full extent of damage to the part and surrounding structural areas. Structural design features may be needed to provide sufficient large damage capability to ensure limit or near limit load is maintained with easily detectable. Structural substantiation includes, in this case, demonstration of a reliable and quick detection, while retaining limit or near limit load capability. Some examples of damages belonging to this category are large VID or other obvious damage that will be caught during walk-around inspection or during the normal course of operations (e.g., fuel leaks, system malfunctions or cabin noise);
- the fourth category includes damages from a known incident such that flight maneuvers are limited. Structural substantiation for damages of this category includes a demonstration of residual strength for loads specified in the regulations. Some examples in this case include rotor burst, bird strikes, tire bursts, and severe in-flight hail;
- the fifth category includes severe damages created by anomalous ground or flight events, which are not covered by design criteria or structural substantiation procedures.

These damages are in the current guidance to ensure the engineers responsible for composite aircraft structure design and the FAA and EASA work with maintenance organizations in making operations personnel aware of possible damage belonging to this fifth category. It is also the responsibility of structural engineers to design sufficient damage resistance such that events belonging to this category are self-evident to the operations personnel involved. Some examples of

damages included in this category are severe service vehicle collisions with aircraft, anomalous flight overload conditions, abnormally hard landings, maintenance jacking errors, and loss of aircraft parts in flight, including possible subsequent high-energy, wide-area impact with adjacent structure.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of design load levels versus categories of damage severity, [5].

Structure details, elements, and subcomponents of critical structural areas should be tested under repeated loads to define the sensitivity of the structure to damage growth. The environment used should be appropriate to the expected service usage. Inspection intervals should be established, considering both the likelihood of a particular damage and the residual strength capability associated with this damage. Once the damage is detected, the component is either repaired to restore ultimate load capability or replaced.

The damage tolerance test articles should be fabricated and assembled in accordance with production specifications and processes so that the test articles are representative of production structure. The extent of initially detectable damage should be established and be consistent with the inspection techniques employed during manufacture and in service. For damage that is clearly detectable to an extent that it will likely be found before scheduled maintenance, detection over shorter intervals and by untrained personnel may be permitted.

Inspection intervals should be established such that the damage will be reliably detected between the time it initially becomes detectable and the time at which the extent of damage reaches the limits for required residual strength capability. The potential for missed inspections should be considered. It should be shown that stiffness properties have not changed beyond acceptable levels. A thorough composite damage threat assessment and the separation of different damage sizes into categories, each with associated detection methods, supports programs using a rigorous damage tolerance assessment to avoid conservative design criteria with very large damage assumptions. Depending on the category of the damage, a particular procedure is required. Despite that, the main target is to make the structure able to withstand loads which are reasonably expected during a completion of the flight on which damage resulting from obvious discrete sources occur.

3.2.2 Fatigue evaluation

Fatigue substantiation should be accomplished by component fatigue tests or by analysis supported by test evidence, accounting for the effects of the appropriate environment. In this kind of tests cyclic loads are used to measure resistance degradation and breakage due to loads varying over time. The frequency of application is generally low to avoid excessive heating of the specimens: in the case of composites, it is between 5 and

10 Hz. The cyclic loads can be of constant amplitude or follow load spectra representative of operating conditions. The test articles should be fabricated and assembled in accordance with production specifications and processes so that the test articles are representative of production structures. Sufficient component, subcomponent, element or coupon tests should be performed to establish the fatigue scatter and the environmental effects. Component, subcomponent, and element tests may be used to evaluate the fatigue response of structure with impact damage levels typical of those that may occur during fabrication, assembly, and in service, consistent with the inspection procedures employed. Other allowed manufacturing and service defects, which would exist for the life of the structure, should also be included in fatigue testing. It should be demonstrated during the fatigue tests that the stiffness properties have not changed beyond acceptable levels.

4 Certification requirements of electrical equipment and installations

The current requirements governing the installation of batteries in Large Aeroplanes are covered by the Certification Specification (CS) 25.1353(c), and the equivalent for normal category 23.1353 (c). The applicable airworthiness codes JAR/CS-25 do not provide standards or specific guidance material. Requirements from CS XX.1353(c) are essentially unchanged from initial JAR code and do not adequately address several failure, operational, and maintenance characteristics of Lithium Batteries that could affect safety and reliability of those battery installations. At the same time, the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and European Agency (EASA) agree that a standardization of test methods is necessary to facilitate certification of new aircraft designs that incorporate a permanently installed rechargeable lithium-ion battery. For new transport airplane certification projects, the FAA issues special conditions for applicants whose designs include rechargeable lithium-ion or other lithium-based batteries. These special conditions provide adequate certification standards. The intent of this Special Condition is to ensure that these rechargeable Lithium battery installations are not unsafe, to an extent necessary to support issuance of an airworthiness certificate.

The FAA worked with the Radio Technical Commission for Aeronautics (RTCA) to approve a revision to RTCA 00-311, *Minimum Operational Performance Standards for Rechargeable Lithium Battery Systems*, for large battery systems. On December 2017, the RTCA released RTCA 00-311A, which contains abuse tests that subject a single cell within a permanently installed, rechargeable lithium-ion battery to thermal runaway and demonstrate that the battery installation mitigates all hazardous effects of propagation to other cells and release of electrolytes, fire, or explosive debris outside the battery case. The tests will replicate the battery installation on the aircraft and be conducted under conditions that are considered to produce the most severe outcome.

On October 2015, the FAA issued the AC 20-184 [7], *Guidance on Testing and Installation of Rechargeable Lithium Battery and Battery Systems on Aircraft*, to provide guidance for complying with the special conditions to meet the installation, operation, maintenance, and airworthiness requirements for installation of lithium batteries on aircraft. AC 20-184 invokes RTCA 00-311 and RTCA 00-347, *Certification Test Guidance for Small and Medium Sized Rechargeable Lithium Batteries and Battery Systems* and provides guidance on how to obtain installation approval for permanently installed rechargeable lithium-ion batteries and battery systems on aircraft.

The FAA is revising AC 20-184 to invoke RTCA 00-311A as one means of compliance to the special conditions regarding rechargeable lithium-ion battery systems. Until the AC 20-184 revision is released, for new transport airplane certification projects, the FAA will use issue papers to inform applicants of the effects of battery cells going into thermal runaway. In the meantime, all current projects will use RTCA 00-311A and RTCA 00-347 as a means of compliance.

4.1 System safety assessment

The system safety assessment must show compliance with §§ 23/25/27/29.1309 and any applicable special condition. This assessment should address concerns associated with the installation of the lithium batteries and battery systems, the possibility of direct (or indirect) injury to a person, any adverse effect on crew function, or any adverse effect on other equipment and systems. These effects could be a result of normal operation or a failure in the lithium batteries. The safety assessment of the lithium batteries installation should address the battery system, the aircraft interface, and the aircraft functional loads to which the battery system provides power. In addition, it should consider:

- The levels of hazard associated with installation and use of the lithium battery.
- Rationale addressing the lithium battery installation design assurance level as appropriate for performance and safety requirements based on location and intended function.
- Ensure no interference due to any failures of the lithium battery.

- System separation and zonal analysis.
- Impact on flight crew and egress procedures.
- Protection against fire, smoke, and electrical shock hazards.
- Other safety analysis appropriate to the system being installed.

4.2 Health monitoring

Lithium batteries should be stored in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations for state of charge and temperature; consideration should be provided for any monitoring circuitry that may drain the battery during the storage period. Additionally, overcharging of individual cells could lead to thermal runaway. Health monitoring of lithium batteries needs to be considered during testing and certification to ensure that proper state of charge can be maintained.

4.3 Flammability

Aircraft batteries must meet the applicable flammability requirements of §§ 23/25/27/29.853, 23/25/27/29.863, and 25.869 that ensure the protection of structure and critical systems. Test the materials to ensure they meet applicable requirements of §§ 23/25/27/29.853, 23/25/27/29.863, and 25.869.

The FAA Aircraft Materials Fire Test Handbook, DOT/FAA/AR-00/12, describes an acceptable means of compliance with 14 CFR part 25, Appendix F. If thermal and acoustic insulation material is used as part of the battery equipment and exposed, the requirements of § 25.856(a), Appendix F, part VI, at amendment 25-111 (or later amendment) must be met. Refer to the test methods described by AC 25.856-1, *Thermal/Acoustic Insulation Flame Propagation Test Method Details*.

4.4 Continued airworthiness

During the certification process of the lithium batteries, the Instructions for Continued Airworthiness (ICA) must respect the following certification basis:

- 14 CFR part 21.50(b);
- 14 CFR part 23/25/27/29.1529;
- 14 CFR parts 25.1709 and 25.1729;
- 14 CFR part 23, Appendix G;
- 14 CFR part 25, Appendix H;
- 14 CFR parts 27/29, Appendix A;
- FAA Order 8110.54, *Instructions for Continued Airworthiness, Responsibilities, Requirements, and Contents*.

The ICA must contain an "Airworthiness Limitations" section if deemed necessary. This section specifies maintenance required under §§ 43.16 and 91.403, unless the FAA has approved an alternative program. The ICA should also include specifics of the lithium batteries installation (including individual component part numbers and any other unique installation requirements), electrical wiring diagrams and equipment drawing. Maintenance instructions, basic control and operation, testing, servicing, maintenance schedule, inspection, troubleshooting, removing, and replacing parts, repairs, special tools, fixtures and equipment, component manual, configuration control and storage instructions should also be contained in the ICA.

Since batteries are installed for safe operation of the aircraft, to ensure them to perform their intended function as long they are installed in the aircraft, the ICA must contain the recommended manufacturer's maintenance and inspection requirements. In addition, the following must be contained:

- Operating instructions and equipment limitations in an installation maintenance manual.
- Installation procedures and limitations sufficient to ensure cells or batteries, when installed according to the installation procedures, still meet the airworthiness requirements of the aircraft. The limitations must identify any unique aspects of the installation.

- Maintenance requirements for measurements of battery capacity at appropriate intervals will be performed to ensure the batteries, whose function is required for safe operation of the aircraft, will continue to meet their intended function if they are installed in the aircraft.
- Scheduled servicing information to replace batteries per the manufacturer's recommendations.
- Maintenance and inspection requirements to visually check for a battery and/or charger degradation.

The ICA should also contain maintenance procedures for lithium batteries in spares storage to prevent the replacement of batteries with batteries that have experienced degraded charge retention ability or other damage due to prolonged storage.

The ICA must contain instructions to replace batteries based on the lithium batteries original equipment manufacturer (OEM) maintenance manual. Replacement of individual cells within lithium batteries must be approved by the lithium battery OEM and the FAA. Mixing of cells from different manufacturers within a lithium battery is not permitted unless an alternate means proposed by the lithium batteries OEM and approved by the FAA exist.

4.5 Aircraft battery maintenance

The battery Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) instructions should be followed since maintenance and inspection requirements for aircraft lithium batteries vary with the type of chemical technology and physical construction. Performance of lithium batteries will depend on several factors that include:

- Lithium Battery Chemistry – The electrolyte and cathode materials used in lithium batteries can be a highly reactive substance; therefore, care must be exercised to maintain them in accordance with their OEM maintenance manual.
- Age – To determine the life and age of the lithium battery, record the manufacturing and/or installation date of the battery. During normal battery maintenance, document battery age in either the aircraft maintenance log or the shop maintenance log. Do not keep batteries in service longer than recommended by the lithium battery manufacturer.
- State of Charge – State of charge of the lithium battery will be determined by the cumulative effect of charging and discharging the battery. Safeguards must be implemented to ensure the aircraft does not begin flight with a battery not sufficiently charged to accomplish the intended function of the lithium battery.
- State of Health – The length of time the battery has been in service, environmental factors (such as excessive heat or cold), observed failures (such as low voltage under load) and battery performance measurements (as specified by the battery manufacturer such as capacity, voltage, internal resistance, etc.) should be accounted for.
- Mechanical Integrity – To ensure proper mechanical integrity, the battery must be installed and connected correctly and be free of any physical damage. The build-up of explosive gases can be avoided by incorporating battery and battery compartment venting systems, which need a periodic check to ensure safe connection and orientation.
- Reliability of Charging/Monitoring Systems – The manufacturer recommendation for maintenance inspections concerning the battery charging and monitoring systems should be respected.
- Aircraft Battery Inspection – Evidence of battery failure can sometimes be detected by a visual inspection. Manufacturer recommended inspections should include the inspection of battery terminals and all other connections for evidence of corrosion, pitting, arcing, and burns; the correct battery installation and mounting and evidence of physical damage if present.

4.6 Aircraft battery replacement

Installation of lithium batteries differs from aircraft system to aircraft system. To remove and install batteries correctly, the applicable aircraft manuals and maintenance procedures should be considered. When replacing batteries, corrosion and moisture on the battery interfaces must be checked. Also checking for short circuit to battery case such as insulation resistance test are required.

4.7 Aircraft battery storage and handling

Storage requirements can vary with the battery type, thus the manufacturer recommended storage procedures should be considered to achieve the best results. Handling procedures and precautions vary with battery size and configuration. Also in this case, the manufacturer recommendation to prevent mishandling of the battery and electrostatic discharge during storage and handling should be considered. For packaging and shipping, the manufacturer recommended procedures should be followed. Batteries should be checked before use for any leakage or deformity.

Aircraft vibration and/or contact oxidation can result in poor electrical connections. Proper connector maintenance procedures should be carefully followed. In addition, precautions must be kept when handling lithium batteries, they should not be stored with other hazardous or combustible materials. Special care in handling lithium batteries should be maintained: batteries must not be opened, punctured, crushed, disassembled, or subjected to physical abuse. Lithium batteries can be a personal safety hazard due to the possibility of lethal shock and must be labelled to clearly indicate the hazard. Material Safety Data Sheets must be enclosed with lithium batteries for shipping.

Special Conditions

The AC 20-184 also contains Special Conditions to consider. These are 9 special conditions, which are supplementary to the information previously provided. They are as follows:

- The cells within the lithium battery system shall be designed to minimize the impact of self-sustained, uncontrolled increases in cell temperature or pressure, because of any foreseeable charging or discharging condition. It must preclude explosion in the event of any failure.
- The lithium battery system shall be designed to minimize the impact of self-sustained, uncontrolled increases in temperature or pressure, because of any failure within the battery.
- The battery system shall not emit any explosive or toxic gases, smoke, or fluids during normal operation except through designed venting provisions. Battery systems shall be capable of containing or safely relieving the maximum pressure build-up that can occur under worst-case failure conditions. If the battery system is not capable of containing the maximum pressure, then the appropriate provisions shall be included to safely relieve pressure from the battery. Emissions shall only escape through designed pressure relief provisions. Hazardous emissions may be flammable, explosive, corrosive, or toxic in certain concentrations. The aircraft installation must be compatible with the emissions and temperatures that the battery or battery system may generate during any failure condition. Any venting provisions on the battery or battery system and containment systems of electrolyte leakage, toxic or explosive gases, and debris are advised.
- Internal and external materials of the rechargeable lithium battery and battery system shall meet the applicable certification flammability requirements of the installation. They must meet the requirements of §§ 23/25/27/29.863(a) through (d).
- There shall be no damage to surrounding structure or any adjacent systems, equipment, or electrical wiring from the fluids or gases emitted from the battery. The design assurance level must meet the requirement of § 23/25/27/29.1309(b/c) and any other applicable airworthiness regulations.
- The lithium battery system shall be designed to minimize the impact of self-sustained, uncontrolled increases in temperature or pressure, because of cell failures (for example, internal cell short circuit) or a short circuit of the battery. It shall prevent any hazardous effect on adjacent or nearby structures or essential systems during this failure.

- The rechargeable lithium battery or battery system shall have protective features to prevent unsafe conditions during operation. The monitoring and protective system shall control the charging rate of the battery automatically to prevent any overcharging or overheating. This includes automatically disconnect charging when this fault occurs.
- Any aircraft that uses a lithium battery or battery system whose function is necessary for safe operation shall require the incorporation of a monitoring and warning feature that will provide an accurate indication to the appropriate flight crewmembers whenever the state-of-charge of the batteries has fallen below levels considered acceptable for dispatch of the aircraft.
- The ICA required by §§ 23/25/27/29.1529 must contain maintenance requirements to assure that the battery is sufficiently charged at appropriate intervals specified by the battery manufacturer and the equipment manufacturer that contain the rechargeable lithium battery or rechargeable lithium battery system. This is required to ensure that lithium rechargeable batteries and lithium rechargeable battery systems will not degrade below specified ampere-hour levels sufficient to power the aircraft system. The ICA must also contain procedures for the maintenance of batteries in spares storage to prevent the replacement of batteries with batteries that have experienced degraded charge retention ability or other damage due to prolonged storage at a low state of charge. Precautions should be included in the ICA maintenance instructions to prevent mishandling of the rechargeable lithium battery and rechargeable lithium battery systems, which could result in short-circuit or other unintentional impact damage caused by dropping or other destructive means that could result in personal injury or property damage. The ICA shall contain maintenance requirements to assure proper maintenance and operation of the rechargeable lithium batteries and battery system.

The same indication is also pointed out in the SC E-19, *Electric/Hybrid Propulsion Systems* [8] which has been developed to support applications received by EASA for the certification of Electric and/or Hybrid Propulsion Systems (EHPS) powered by propulsion batteries and/or fuel. Thus, it should be considered when an aircraft is equipped with Structural Batteries.

5 Conclusions

In this report general considerations about certification requirements on composite material structures and the current trend of certification agencies to move towards a performance-based regulations have been addressed. This document may represent a reference for structural composite batteries, for which there are still no well-defined certification requirements.

Structural batteries, however, have also an energy-storing function, so they have also to meet airworthiness requirement applied on aircraft batteries.

Until structural performance characteristics are not fully understood and can't be generalized, the use of conservative, simplified engineering approaches with point design substantiation, followed with a more rigorous, fully developed building block approach for expanded applications is recommended.

Thus, assuming this approach is valid, it is possible, e.g., to treat a composite laminate in which a structural battery is integrated as a laminate in which a delamination has occurred evolving the current regulatory activities, and which meets the structural and electrical requirements considering that:

- regarding the structural aspect, the concept of damage tolerance and fatigue assessment of the structure, a strength assessment, detail design and fabrication shall demonstrate that catastrophic failure due to fatigue, manufacturing defects, deterioration Environmental (ED) or Accidental Damage (AD) will be avoided for the operational life of the aircraft systems [10].
- regarding the aspect of the interaction between systems and structure, for aircraft equipped with systems that affect structural performance, either directly or as a result of a failure or malfunction, the influence of these systems and their failure conditions shall be considered when demonstrating compliance with airworthiness requirements, to evaluate the structural performance of airplanes equipped with these systems, [10].

Continuing this approach, the European community has in fact founded various activities in H2020. Examples are the ACACIAS (Advanced Concepts for Aero-Structures with Integrated Antenna and Sensors) project, focused primarily on the realization of a fuselage panel with integrated sensors and wiring for reduction of cabin noise and a smart winglet with integrated blade antenna [11]. Similarly, the MORPHO (Manufacturing, Overhaul, Repair for Prognosis Health Overreach) project proposes to embed printed fiber-optical sensors in aircraft engine fan blades, thus providing them with cognitive capabilities already while they are manufactured [12]. Finally, DOMMINIO (Digital method for imprOved Manufacturing of next generation Multifunctional airframe parts) project presents as objectives the innovative multifunctional thermoplastic filaments fibre-based piezoresistive strain sensors employed to incorporate novel continuous carbon nanotubes in the laminate [13].

Experts from the European agency EASA, Dr. Simon Waite (materials expert) for the structures panel and Dr. Carlos Javier Muñoz García (new electrical technologies) for the electrical panel, voluntarily assisted in the examination and documentation of the work presented in this deliverable and provided indications in compliance with aeronautical regulations. They have our gratitude for their assistance.

6 References

- [1] <https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/Report%20A%20Harmonised%20European%20Approach%20to%20a%20Performance%20Based%20Environment.pdf>
- [2] <https://www.acquisition.gov/far/part-25>
- [3] <https://agate.niar.wichita.edu/>
- [4] https://www.wichita.edu/industry_and_defense/NIAR/Research/ncamp.php
- [5] FAA. AC20-107B: Composite Aircraft Structure. 2009.
- [6] AMC 20-29 (CS-23 – commuter aircraft, CS-25, CS-27 and CS-29), 2010.
- [7] FAA. AC20-184: Guidance on Testing and Installation of Rechargeable Lithium Battery and Battery Systems on Aircraft. 2015.
- [8] EASA. SC E-19: Electric/Hybrid Propulsion Systems (EHPS). 2019.
- [9] EASA CS-23, Certification Specifications for Normal-Category Aeroplanes, CS-23 Amendment 6, 2023.
- [10] EASA CS-25, Certification Specifications for Large Aeroplanes, CS 25 Amendment 27, 2023.
- [11] <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723167>
- [12] <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006854>
- [13] <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101007022>

Project partners

Participant No*	Participant short name	Participant organization name	Country
1. (Coord.)	AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	Austria
2.	ONERA	Office national d'études et de recherches aérospatiales	France
3.	CCI	Custom Cells Itzehoe GmbH	Germany
4.	UNIVIE	University of Vienna	Austria
5.	UNINA	Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	Italy
6.	CIRA	Centro Italiano Ricerche Aerospaziali	Italy

This project receives funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101007577.

This publication reflects only the author's view. The European Commission and the CleanSky 2 Joint Undertaking are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.